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DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF STABILITY INDICATING RP-HPLC METHOD FOR THE ESTIMATION OF CABOZANTINIB IN PHARMACEUTICAL DOSAGE FORM

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Abstract : A simple, specific, accurate and stability-indicating reversed phase high performance liquid chromatographic (RP-HPLC) method was developed for the estimation of Cabozantinib, using a reversed-phase C18 column (250 mm × 4.6 mm, 5 μm) a mobile phase consisting of 0.1% Formic acid:acetonitrile:methanol (35:33:32 v/v), at a flow rate of 1.0 mL/min and ultraviolet detection at 244 nm. The retention time of cabozantinib was found to be 6.03 min. Linearity was established in the range of 100-500 μg/mL with correlation coefficients 0.990. The percentage recoveries of cabozantinib were found to be in the range of 99.59-99.96%. Stress testing was carried out to demonstrate specificity of the method. The developed method could separate the potential degradation products from the cabozantinib. This proposed method was suitable for analysis the content of cabozantinib in tablet dosage form. The method is validated as per ICH guidelines.

Index Terms - Cabozantinib, HPLC, Stability-indicating method, Validation

1. INTRODUCTION

In drug development, stability studies are an integral part as for any drug candidate, the chemical integrity of the active pharmaceutical ingredient must be maintained until the drug is delivered to the intended site of action. Instability of drug affect the bioavailability, overall performance of formulation and eventually to toxic effects.^[1] International Conference on Harmonization (ICH) has made mandatory requirement of stability-indicating assay method (SAIM) for every drug candidate.^[2-3] A SAIM is a validated qualitative analytical procedure that can detect the changes with time in the properties of the drug product and drug substance under defined storage condition.^[2-3] As per ICH guideline forced degradation of the drug substance aids in identifying degradation products, mechanism of breakdown, and appropriate methodology for assessing stability it can also help in establishing the degradation pathway.^[2-4]

Cabozantinib is an orally bioavailable, small molecule receptor tyrosine kinase (RTK) inhibitor with potential antineoplastic activity. It is indicated for the treatment of metastatic medullary thyroid cancer.^[5] Cabozantinib is chemically known as N-(4-((6, 7-Dimethoxyquinolin-4-yl)oxy)phenyl)-N'-(4-fluorophenyl)cyclopropane-1,1-dicarboxamide.^[6] Cabozantinib is a kinase inhibitor that inhibits the tyrosine kinase activity of MET, VEGFR-1, -2 and -3, AXL, RET, ROS1, TYRO3, MER, KIT, TRKB, FLT-3, and TIE-2.^[7-9] These receptor tyrosine kinases are involved in both normal cellular function and pathologic processes such as oncogenesis, metastasis, tumor angiogenesis, drug resistance, and maintenance of the tumor microenvironment.^[7-9] The chemical structure of CABO is shown in Fig.1. Literature study reveals that there are few methods for determining in plasma and in pharmaceutical dosage forms^[10-14]. Therefore, the present study was aimed to develop and validate a simple, precise and economical RP-HPLC method. A validated stability indicating assay method must be employed to study the influence of storage on quality, safety and/or efficacy of a drug substance. Stress studies must be performed early in development phase to assess inherent stability of a drug. Validation of stability indicating assay method is essential to prove that it distinguishes active ingredients from degradation products and can measure their content without interference. We report here the development of a validated reversed phase high performance liquid chromatography (RPHPLC) method for analysis of Cabozantinib and its successful application as a stability indicating assay. The proposed method was validated according to ICH guidelines and its updated international convention.^[15-23]

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1. Chemicals and reagents

An HPLC grade acetonitrile, methanol and formic acid were procured from Finar Chemicals Limited, Ahmadabad. Water-HPLC grade was procured from Finar Chemicals Limited, Ahmadabad. Distilled water was obtained from Milli Q water system in laboratory. Cabozantinib Working Standard was procured Spectrum Labs, Hyderabad, India as a gift sample. The marketed formulation of cabozantinib was procured from local market.

2.2. Instrumentation and chromatographic conditions

An isocratic HPLC system of waters 2640 UV detector having software Empower 2 was used for chromatographic analysis. The chromatographic conditions were optimized and these were as shown in Table 1. A representative chromatogram is shown in Fig. 2.

2.3. Solution preparation

Preparation of mobile phase

1 mL of 100% Formic acid is diluted with 1000 mL HPLC grade water for making 0.1% formic acid in water, then taking 35 part of 0.1 % formic acid in water, 33 parts of ACN and 32 parts of methanol and mixed well, then degassed by sonicator and solution used as a mobile phase

Preparation of diluent

Mobile phase used as a diluent.

Preparation of Standard stock solution:

Accurately weighed 10 mg Cabozantinib working standard was transferred into 10 mL volumetric flasks. Drug was dissolved in 5 mL diluent and diluted up to mark with diluent, to achieve final concentration of 1000 µg/mL.

Preparation of Working Standard solution:

From the standard stock solution, pipetted out 1 mL into 100 mL volumetric flasks and diluted up to the mark with diluent to prepare 10 µg/mL of Cabozantinib.

Preparation of Sample solution:

20 tablets (Newgen Life Science, Lucicaboz Tab) were triturated after taking their average weight. The tablet powder equivalent to 10 mg was transferred into a 100 mL volumetric flask and dissolved in acetonitrile with sonication for 15 min. The solution was filtered through 0.45 µm membrane filter and the residues were washed thoroughly with ACN. The filtrate and washings were combined in a 100 mL volumetric flask and diluted to the mark with ACN to get a final concentration of 100 µg/mL of Cabozantinib. The concentration of sample solution was found from regression equation of CABO.

2.4. Method validation

The developed HPLC method was validated according to ICH guidelines in terms of precision, ruggedness, linearity, specificity, selectivity, robustness and accuracy.

Linearity (Calibration curve):

Calibration curves were plotted over concentration range of 100-500 µg/mL of CABO. Accurately measured solutions of CABO (1, 2, 3, 4, 5) were transferred to a series of 10 mL of volumetric flasks from the standard stock preparation of CABO (1000 µg/mL) and diluted to the mark with diluent. The solutions were injected into the LC system and chromatograms were recorded. Regression equation was computed by constructing calibration curve. Calibration curve of CABO is shown in Fig. 3. The linearity was observed in the expected concentration range, demonstrating its suitability for analysis (Fig. 4).

Specificity and selectivity:

Stress studies of the drug product are utilized for identification of the possible degradation products and for the validation of the stability indicating analytical procedure. It is the ability of the analytical method to measure analyte response in the presence of its degradation products and sample matrix.

Precision:

Method precision (% Repeatability):

The precision of the instrument was checked by repeatedly injecting (n = 6) solution of CABO (100 µg/mL). The results were reported in term of % coefficient of variance (% CV) should not more than 2 %.

Intermediate precision (reproducibility):

The intra-day and inter-day precision study (intermediate precision) was carried out by estimating the responses 3 times on the same day and on 3 different days for three different concentrations of CABO (200,300,400 µg/mL) and the results were reported in terms of %RSD.

Accuracy (recovery study):

The accuracy of the method was determined by the standard addition method in which Cabozantinib standard solutions (80,100, and 120%) were added to the preanalyzed solution of drug. The amounts of CABO were estimated by applying obtained values to the regression line equations. The experiment was repeated for three times.

Limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantitation (LOQ):

Determination of signal-to-noise ratio was calculated under the proposed chromatographic condition. LOD was considered as 3:1 and LOQ as 10:1.

Robustness:

Robustness of the method was performed by deliberately changing the experimental conditions like flow rate and wavelength.

System suitability:

A system suitability test was an integral part of the method development to check that the system is appropriate for the analysis of CABO to be performed. System suitability test of the chromatography system was performed before validation runs. Retention time (RT), Theoretical plates and Tailing factor for the five suitability injections were determined.

Analysis of commercial tablet formulation:

The ability of the optimized method to determine CABO in a commercial drug product was tested using six individual preparations. The Tablets contain 20 mg of CABO.

2.5. Forced degradation studies:

Forced degradation studies of the drugs were carried out under conditions of hydrolysis, oxidation, neutral, photolytic and thermal.

Alkali Hydrolysis:

Forced degradation in basic media was performed by dissolving 10 mg drug in 1 mL acetonitrile in 10 mL volumetric flask and diluted up to mark with 1N NaOH. Then this solution was kept at 80°C for reflux. Sample was withdrawn at 0 min, after 1,2,3,4 and 5 Hours. Pipetted out 0.3 mL of this solution in 10 mL volumetric flask and neutralized with 0.3 mL 1 N HCl and diluted up to the mark with acetonitrile.

Acid Hydrolysis:

Forced degradation in acidic media was performed by dissolving 10 mg drug in 1 mL acetonitrile in 10 mL volumetric flask and diluted up to mark with 1N HCl. Then this solution was kept at 80°C for reflux. Sample was withdrawn at 0 min, after 1, 2, 3 and 4 Hours. Pipetted out 0.3 mL of this solution in 10 mL volumetric flask and neutralized with 0.3 mL 1 N NaOH and diluted upto the mark with acetonitrile.

Hydrolysis at neutral pH (water degradation)

Forced degradation at neutral pH in water was performed by dissolving 10 mg drug in 1 mL acetonitrile in 10 mL volumetric flask and diluted up to mark with water. Then this solution was kept at 80°C for reflux. Sample was withdrawn at 0 min, after 10 min, 30 min, 1, 2, 3 and 4 Hours. Pipetted out 0.3 mL of this solution in 10 mL volumetric flask and diluted up to the mark with acetonitrile.

Oxidative Hydrolysis:

Oxidative stress degradation was performed by dissolving 10 mg drug in 1 mL acetonitrile in 10 mL volumetric flask and diluted up to mark with 30 % H₂O₂. Then this solution was kept at room temperature. Sample was withdrawn at 0 min. and after 48 Hours. Pipetted out 0.3 mL of this solution in 10 mL volumetric flask and diluted up to the mark with ACN.

Thermal Hydrolysis:

For thermal degradation, Drug (CABO) kept in Petri dish into the oven at 80° for 3 hr. Thereafter, 10 mg of CABO was weighed and transferred to 10 mL volumetric flasks and diluted up to the mark with acetonitrile. Pipetted out 0.3 mL of this solution in 10 mL volumetric flask and diluted upto the mark with acetonitrile.

Photolytic Degradation:

The photo stability was also studied by exposing drug at direct sunlight for 6 Hour. Thereafter, 10 mg of CABO was weighed and transferred to 10 mL volumetric flasks and diluted up to the mark with acetonitrile. Pipetted out 0.3 mL of this solution in 10 mL volumetric flask and diluted upto the mark with acetonitrile.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The mobile phase consisting of 0.1% Formic acid in Water: Acetonitrile: Methanol (35:33:32v/v), at 1 mL/min flow rate was optimised which gave good peak shape with clear baseline was obtained within very short retention time. For selection of wavelength of determination, drug solution was scanned in the range of 200 to 400 nm and maximum absorbance for drug was obtained at 244 nm. The system suitability results including theoretical plate, tailing factor are shown in Table 2.

In order to ensure that the method is suitable for its intended use, method validation has been performed according to the ICH guideline. The method validation parameters were linearity, precision, accuracy, LOD and LOQ. The calibration curves were constructed from the area versus the concentration of the standards and showed that the method was linear across the range of 100–500 µg/mL with good correlation coefficient ($r^2 = 0.990$) (Table 3). The linearity of the calibration curve was validated by the high values of correlation coefficient of regression. The RSD values for repeatability were found to be 0.122 % (Table 4). The relative standard deviation (less than 2%) indicates that the proposed method is repeatable. The RSD values of intraday (0.01 – 0.02%) and interday (0.01-0.04%) reveal that the proposed method is precise (Table 5). The recovery experiment was performed by the standard addition method. The mean % recovery data of CABO showed results between 99.59- 99.96% (Table 6). The results of recovery studies indicate that the proposed method is accurate. The LOD and LOQ were measured theoretically and were found to be 0.406 and 1.231 µg/mL (Table 3). No interference of the excipients with the response of interest appeared; hence the proposed method is applicable for the routine analysis of Cabozantinib pharmaceutical dosage forms. No significant changes were observed during the deliberate change in the experimental conditions. The modifications included different mobile phase flow rates of (± 0.1 ml/min) and wavelength variations (± 2 nm) were also investigated. The % RSD values showed no significant change in the results of each of the ingredients using variations (Table 7).

The degradation study indicated that the drug degrades as shown by the decreased areas in the peaks when compared with peak areas of the same concentration of the non degraded drug, without giving any additional degradation peaks. Percent degradation was calculated by comparing the areas of the degraded peaks in each degradation condition with the corresponding areas of the peak of the drug under non degradation condition. Conditions used for forced degradation are mentioned in Table 8. The % degradation was found to be 4 to 100% of CABO in the given condition using developed HPLC method (Fig. 5-10). Summary of degradation studies of the drug is given in Table 9. Present study indicates the suitability of reversed-phase column procedure for the analysis of Cabozantinib in Pharmaceutical dosage form. The percentage of Cabozantinib was found to be satisfactory, which is comparable with the corresponding claim amount results given in Table 10. The labeled amount of Cabozantinib 20 mg/tablet recovered 100.18%. It can be concluded that the method is simple, accurate, and precise.

4. Conclusion

Stability-indicating HPLC method was developed and validated for routine qualitative and quantitative analysis of CABO in a tablet dosage form. The method is stability-indicating, and therefore qualified and reliable for demonstrating and detecting any expected change or degradation in the drug product during stability studies. The method is robust and rugged enough to reproduce accurate and precise results under different method conditions.

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TABLE 1: CONDITIONS OF OPTIMIZED RP-HPLC METHOD

Method Parameters	Optimized value
Column	phenomenax C18 (250×4.6mm, 5μ)
Analytical Wavelength	244 nm
Mobile phase	0.1% Formic acid in Water: Acetonitrile: Methanol (35:33:32 v/v)
Pump mode	Isocratic
Flow rate	1.0 mL/min
Volume of Injection	10 μL
Run Time	10 min.

TABLE 2: SYSTEM SUITABILITY RESULTS OF THE PROPOSED METHOD

Parameters	CABO
Retention time (Minutes)	6.03
Theoretical plates (TP)	6399
Tailing factor (Tf)	0.67

TABLE 3: METHOD VALIDATION PARAMETERS FOR THE QUANTITATION OF CABO

Parameters	Cabozantinib
Linear range ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	100-500
Regression equation	$y = 582.5x - 4454$
Correlation coefficient (r^2)	0.990
Slope	582.5
Intercept	4454
LOQ ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	1.231
LOD ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	0.406

TABLE 4: METHOD PRECISION DATA OF CABO

Name	Area of CABO
Method Precision-1	58466
Method Precision-2	58420
Method Precision-3	58590
Method Precision-4	58575
Method Precision-5	58568
Method Precision-6	58580
Mean	58533
SD	71.70
% RSD	0.122

TABLE 5: INTER-DAY AND INTRA-DAY PRECISION DATA OF CABO

Drug	Conc. $\mu\text{g/mL}$	Intra-day measured mean area \pm % RSD (n=3)	Inter-day measured mean area \pm % RSD (n=3)
CABO	200	116230.7 \pm 0.02	116217.3 \pm 0.03
	300	154606.3 \pm 0.02	154636.3 \pm 0.04
	400	228533.7 \pm 0.01	228535.7 \pm 0.01

TABLE 6: RECOVERY DATA OF PROPOSED METHOD

Drug	Level	Amount taken ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Amount added ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Amount recovered ($\mu\text{g/mL}$) (n=3)	Mean % Recovery (n=3)
CABO	80%	100	80	179.28	99.59
	100%	100	100	199.46	99.73
	120%	100	120	219.93	99.96

TABLE 7: ROBUSTNESS DATA OF CABO

Parameter	Sr. No	Values	Area	Average	SD	% RSD
Wavelength	1	242 nm	1191349	1191347	31.533	0.003
	2	244 nm	1191378			
	3	246 nm	1191315			
Flow	1	1.0 mL/ min	1191349	1191279	138.673	0.012
	2	1.1 mL/min	1191120			
	3	0.9 mL/min	1191370			

TABLE 8: CONDITIONS GENERALLY EMPLOYED FOR FORCED DEGRADATION

Degradation Type	Experimental Condition	Storage Condition	Sampling Time
Hydrolysis	Control API (no acid or base)	80°C	-
	Acid Control (no API)	80°C	-
	Base Control (no API)	80°C	-
	1N HCl	80°C	0,1,2,3 & 4 Hrs
	1N NaOH	80°C	0,10 min,1,2,3,4 & 5.30 Hrs
Neutral	Water control (no API)	80°C	-
	Water	80°C	0,10 min,30 min,1,2,3 & 4 Hrs
Oxidation	Peroxide Control	RT	-
	30% H ₂ O ₂	RT	48 Hrs
Photolytic	Sunlight	NA	Sunlight (6hr,summer)
Thermal	Oven	80°C	3 Hrs

TABLE 9: SUMMARY OF DEGRADATION STUDIES

Sr. No	Parameters (Stress condition /duration/state)	% of undergrad CABO	% of individual Degradation products		Total % Deg.
1	Neutral/H ₂ O at pH 7/4 h	82	18	-	18
2	Acidic/1 N HCl/4 h/R	07	83	17	93
3	Alkali/1 N NaOH/5.30 h/ Ref.	00	80	20	100
4	Oxidative/30% H ₂ O ₂ /48 h	95	-	-	5
5	Photo/sun light/6 h	91	-	-	9
6	Thermal/80°C/3 h	96	-	-	4

TABLE 10: ASSAY RESULTS FOR CABO IN FORMULATION

Formulation	Label claim (mg)	Amount found (mg)	% Assay ± SD
Lucicaboz	20	20.04	100.18 ± 0.77

Fig. 1: Chemical structures of Cabozantinib

FIG. 2: CHROMATOGRAM OF CABOZANTINIB

Fig. 3: Calibration curve of Cabozantinib

Fig. 4: Linearity of Cabozantinib

(a)

(b)

Fig. 5: Chromatograms of (a) Blank and (b) CABO in 1N NaOH at 0 min, after 10 min, 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5.30 hrs reflux at 80^o C

Fig. 6: Chromatograms of (a) Blank and (b) CABO in 1 N HCL at 0 min, after 1, 2, 3 and 4 hrs reflux at 80 °C.

Fig. 7: Chromatograms of CABO in Neutral condition at 0 min, after 10 min, 30 min, 1 hr, 2 hr, 3 hr and 4 hr reflux at 80° C

Fig. 8: Chromatograms of CABO in 30 % H₂O₂ after 48 hrs

Fig. 9: Chromatograms of thermal degradation of CABO after 3 hrs

Fig. 10: Chromatograms of Photolytic degraded CABO

TABLE AND FIGURE TITLES AND LEGENDS:

TABLE 1: CONDITIONS OF OPTIMIZED RP-HPLC METHOD

TABLE 2: SYSTEM SUITABILITY RESULTS OF THE PROPOSED METHOD

CABO is Cabozantinib.

TABLE 3: METHOD VALIDATION PARAMETERS FOR THE QUANTITATION OF CABO

CABO is Cabozantinib, LOQ is Limit of Quantification, LOD is Limit of Detection, X is the concentration of CABO $\mu\text{g/mL}$, Y is peak area.

TABLE 4: METHOD PRECISION DATA OF CABO

CABO is Cabozantinib, SD is Standard Deviation, RSD is Relative Standard Deviation.

TABLE 5: INTER-DAY AND INTRA-DAY PRECISION DATA OF CABO

CABO is Cabozantinib.

TABLE 6: RECOVERY DATA OF PROPOSED METHOD

CABO is Cabozantinib.

TABLE 7: ROBUSTNESS DATA OF CABO

CABO is Cabozantinib.

TABLE 8: CONDITIONS GENERALLY EMPLOYED FOR FORCED DEGRADATION

API is Active Pharmaceutical Ingredient, H₂O₂ is Hydrogen Peroxide.

TABLE 9: SUMMARY OF DEGRADATION STUDIES

CABO is Cabozantinib, H₂O is the water, Ref is Reflux, - represents no degradation observed.

TABLE 10: ASSAY RESULTS FOR CABO IN FORMULATION

CABO is Cabozantinib.

Fig. 1: Chemical structures of Cabozantinib

FIG. 2: CHROMATOGRAM OF CABOZANTINIB

CABOZANTINIB (CBZ, PEAK 1) WITH t_R OF 6.03 MIN.

Fig. 3: Calibration curve of Cabozantinib

Fig. 4: Linearity of Cabozantinib

Fig. 5: Chromatograms of (a) Blank and (b) CABO in 1N NaOH at 0 min, after 10 min, 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5.30 hrs reflux at 80⁰ C

CABO is Cabozantinib, Cabozantinib peak (CBZ) with t_R of 6.3 min and degradation product A with a t_R of 4.1 min.

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CABO is Cabozantinib, Cabozantinib peak (CBZ) with t_R of 6.3 min.

Undertaking to be signed by all authors while submitting manuscript

We the undersigned herewith submit a manuscript entitled Development and validation of stability indicating RP-HPLC method for the estimation of cabozantinib in pharmaceutical dosage form author by Dr. Rina B. Patel, Dr. Harsha U. Patel and Unnati Patel for consideration for publication as a Research Paper International Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.

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